

Organizational and managerial bases of activity of the Kharkiv Regional Sumo Federation

Ruslan Bairamov
Anastasia Bondar

Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture, Kharkiv, Ukraine

Purpose: to characterize the organizational and managerial bases for the activity of the Kharkiv Regional Sumo Federation.

Material & Methods: the study analyzed the Charter of the Kharkiv Regional Sumo Federation, training programs on sumo, to assess the activities of the Federation a survey was conducted among residents of the Kharkiv region, 230 people took part in it from 17 to 55 years, the sample type is random, the sample calculation was carried out according to the standard methodology, the SWOT analysis was used to assess the environment of the federation, 15 specialists from the sphere of physical culture and sports took part in it.

Results: revealed that the public organization "Kharkiv Regional Sumo Federation" was registered in 2009 with the aim of promoting the development of sumo, acting on the basis of the Charter. In the Kharkiv region, 94 athletes are engaged in sumo, while 48.7% of the surveyed residents of the Kharkiv region consider sumo as an unpopular sport in our country, 76% of respondents are not interested in this sport at all, and only 4.3% are interested, while a low level of awareness has been revealed population of sumo in the region. 80% of respondents consider it necessary to develop sumo in the Kharkiv region.

Conclusions: the results obtained complement and expand modern scientific data on the development of non-Olympic sports, sumo development, methods of teaching sumo. The study determined the state of development of sumo in the Kharkiv region, the structure, activities of the public organization of physical culture and sports direction "Kharkiv Regional Sumo Federation" in accordance with the Charter. Surveys of ordinary citizens showed that, in the opinion of most of them, the Federation should intensify marketing activities, increase the number of broadcasts of competitions on television, create official websites of federations and clubs on the Internet. Estimates of experts confirm the opinion of citizens, the greatest opportunities for the further development of the federation are opened by the popularization of sumo among the population and the expansion of the range of the federation itself, the improvement of quality and advertising of its services, as well as legislative changes. According to ordinary citizens and according to experts, the state should have the least impact on the development of sumo in our country and on the activities of the Federation.

Keywords: sumo, federation, Charter, activities, marketing activities.

Introduction

In recent years, in our country, along with other non-Olympic sports, sumo has been actively developing. This is facilitated by the activities of the Sports Committee of Ukraine and the creation of an extensive system of physical education and sports organizations in this sport led by the national federation. In their scientific works of A. Borisov (2013; 2016), E. Imas (2016), S. Matveev (2016), E. Savarets (2012) reviewed the history of non-Olympic sports and its modern structure, in the works of N. Dolbishevoy (2014; 2015; 2016) described the organizational structure, functions, activities of the governing bodies of domestic non-Olympic sports, N. Sereda (2015) studied the marketing activities of physical education and sports organizations with non-Olympic sports. However, among the works of modern authors there are no issues related to improving the management system of sumo in our country. It should be noted that only a few studies of domestic scientists are devoted to sumo, in particular, G. Arzyutova (2000) studied the rules of sumo wrestling, S. Bezkorovainy (2018), S. Korobko (2004), V. Yaremenko, I. Malinsky, M. Ko-

los V. Shandrigos (2011) proved the effectiveness of the use of sumo elements in the physical education of students to improve the health of students and meet their desire to engage in exotic sports. To popularize sumo among school-age children, the authors of N. Smag, S. Korobko, A. Rebrin (2017) developed a variant module "Sumo", which is included in the "Physical Education Curriculum for General Education Institutions, Grades 5-9" [5], in addition, the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine approved the Sumo program for youth sports schools (2014) [3], which presents the methodology of sports training of sumo players at different stages of sports training. Today, unfortunately, there are no normative documents of the state level, which determined the mechanism of interaction of all subjects of the sphere of physical culture, contributing to the development of sumo.

Purpose of the study: to characterize the organizational and managerial bases for the activity of the Kharkiv Regional Sumo Federation.

Material and Methods of the research

At the first stage of the study, the scientific and methodological literature on the history and development of sumo in Ukraine, the problems of international and domestic non-Olympic sports, and sports management was analyzed with the aim of posing the problem of research and the formation of a scientific apparatus. At the second stage, statistical reports were analyzed in the form of 2-FC and the Charter of the public organization "Kharkiv Regional Sumo Federation" to determine the state of development of sumo in the Kharkiv region and features of the federation's activities. To identify the weaknesses and strengths of the federation's marketing activities, a SWOT analysis was used; 15 specialists in the field of physical culture and sports took part in assessing the external environment, including members of the Kharkiv Regional Sumo Federation, coaches, athletes, directors of youth sports schools, and teachers of the Kharkov State Academy of Physical Culture. To assess the activities of the Kharkiv regional sumo federation in the region, a sociological survey was carried out among residents of the Kharkiv region, in which 230 respondents aged 17–55 years old took part, the sample type was random, the calculation of the sample was carried out according to the standard method of sociological research. At the third stage, the results are systematized and analyzed, the main conclusions of the research are formulated.

Results of the research

In modern sumo there are two directions: professional and amateur. Professional sumo (Ozu) exists only in Japan, where the main governing body is the Japanese Sumo Association (JSA). In all other countries of the world, amateur sumo is developing; for this, the International Sumo Federation (ISF) has been created with headquarters in Tokyo [10; 12].

The international sumo federation has more than 80 countries, the European sumo federation has about 30 countries. In Ukraine, sumo began its existence in 1999. The official status of the All-Ukrainian Sumo Federation was received in 2001, and in 2013 the Federation received the status of a national one and today it has the full name Public Organization All-Ukrainian Public Organization Sumo Federation of Ukraine [8]. In addition, in our country, separate divisions of the national sports federation, including 22 regional and 3 city federations, are engaged in the development and popularization of sumo [7].

To obtain the status of a national, in the manner prescribed by law, the federation must fulfill certain qualification requirements, namely:

- develop sumo throughout the country;
- have membership in the International Federation, included in the list of the State Committee of Youth Policy of Sport and Tourism of Ukraine (now the Ministry of Youth and Sports of Ukraine);
- organize and conduct official international and all-Ukrainian competitions;

- availability of qualification personnel (athletes, coaches, judges and specialists with appropriate qualifications and work experience);
- availability of the necessary logistical and information base, organizational and methodological support [11].

The Sumo Public Organization "Kharkiv Regional Sumo Federation", which according to the register of public associations was registered in 2009, is engaged in the development of sumo in the Kharkiv region. In the Kharkiv region, 94 people are engaged in sumo, 50 of whom are members of a separate division of the national sports federation; 9 physical education and sports workers conduct training sessions: 4 full-time coaches for sports, coaches, teachers, sports teachers and 5 coaches of a separate division of the national sports federation, 1 of whom has the title of Honored Coach of Ukraine [2]. Among Kharkiv athletes are 11 members of the national sumo national team of Ukraine, champions and prize-winners of international competitions.

Public organization "Kharkiv Regional Sumo Federation" (hereinafter referred to as the Federation) is a public organization founded on the basis of the commonality of citizens' interests for the purpose and purpose of the Charter [6]. The main purpose of the Federation's activity is to protect the legitimate interests of its members and to promote the development of sumo in the city of Kharkiv and the Kharkiv region. The Federation is a non-profit organization that is created and operates in accordance with the Constitution of Ukraine, the Law of Ukraine "On Public Associations", the Law of Ukraine "On Physical Culture and Sports", other laws of Ukraine and its own Charter. Members of the Federation may be citizens of Ukraine, foreigners and stateless persons who are legally in Ukraine who recognize the principles, objectives, directions and the Statute of the Federation, promote their implementation, pay membership fees.

The governing and supervising bodies of the Federation are the Conference, the Presidium, the Supervisory Board. The Federation officials are: the President of the Federation, the Vice-Presidents of the Federation, the Chairman and members of the Supervisory Board. The supreme governing body of the Federation is the Conference, which is convened by the Presidium of the Federation at least once a year. An extraordinary Conference is convened by the President of the Federation, the Supervisory Board or at the request of the majority of the Federation members.

The competence of the Conference of the Federation includes the solution of such issues as: adoption of the program of the Federation's activities; amendments to the Federation Charter; election and recall of the Presidium and the Supervisory Board; hearing and approval of reports on the activities of the Presidium and the Supervisory Board of the Federation; the decision to terminate the Federation, the appointment of a liquidation commission, the approval of the liquidation balance sheet; realization in accordance with the procedure established by law the right of ownership to the property of the Federation

The governing body of the Federation, acting between conferences, is the Federation Presidium. The Presidium of the Federation is elected from the membership of the Federation for a term of 5 years and is headed by the President of the Federation. The Presidium of the Federation consists of three people, ex officio the President of the Federation, two vice-presidents of the Federation. The President of the Federation is elected from among the members of the Federation for a term of 5 years and heads the Federation Presidium.

President of the Federation during the rule, manages current activities and performs other functions, for example:

- concludes any transactions and contracts on behalf of the Federation;
- has the right to first sign financial documents;
- opens and closes accounts in banks;
- by decision of the Conference, carries out the operational management of the property of the Federation, subject to restrictions that may be established by the Conference of the Federation;
- approves the staffing of the Federation;
- recruits and dismisses full-time employees of the Federation, and also concludes contracts with specialists to resolve issues related to the activities of the Federation [6].

In accordance with its charter, the regional federation, like many other public organizations, is an independent organization. However, she coordinates all her decisions regarding the global development of sumo in the region with the regional Youth and Sports Administration and the Sumo Federation of Ukraine, namely: the regional federation annually signs a cooperation agreement with the Youth and Sports Administration of the regional state administration, according to which the federation has the right to promote the development of sumo, promote this sport, approve the regional team for official competitions and training camps, as well as organizing and conducting official international, all-Ukrainian and regional competitions in the Kharkiv region. The Department in turn exercises control over the activities of the Federation in the established manner and within its competence [1].

All competitions that take place on the territory of the region included in the regional calendar plan of sports and recreation and sporting events, approved by the Kharkiv Regional State Administration on the proposal of the federation. International and All-Ukrainian competitions, which take place in the region, are held under the general guidance of the Ministry of Youth and Sports of Ukraine and the Sumo Federation of Ukraine. The direct management and preparation of competitions is conducted by the Office of Youth Affairs and Sports of the Regional State Administration, and for the conduct of all-Ukrainian practice-training session, which take place in the territory of the region, the All-Ukrainian Federation and the regional federation are in compliance. Thus, in the Kharkiv region, all practice-training session of domestic sumo athletes from the special preparedness are held annually, in particular, in 2017 seven practice-training sessions were held, in 2018 – 10, in 2019 there are also scheduled 10 practice-training ses-

sion [1].

A survey among residents of the Kharkiv region showed that only 8,3% of respondents consider sumo a popular sport in Ukraine, 40,4% said that sumo is, in their opinion, an unpopular sport in our country, but is developing rapidly, and 48,7 % believe that sumo is a completely unpopular sport.

It is interesting that 69% of respondents consider sumo a spectacular sport, and 31% – no. To the question "Are you interested in news about sumo?" The overwhelming majority of the respondents – 76% answered that they were not interested, 19,7% chose the option "sometimes look" and only 4,3% of respondents are interested in sumo news regularly. The study showed that, despite the fact that most respondents consider sumo a spectacular sport, it does not cause them interest.

Only 40% of respondents know that international sumo competitions are held in Kharkiv, and only 30% know where sumo can be practiced in Kharkiv and Kharkiv region. This indicates a low level of awareness of sumo in the region.

It turned out that 80% of respondents consider it necessary to develop sumo in the Kharkiv region, for this, according to respondents, there are several ways presented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Ways of development of sumo, according to respondents

The figure shows that the majority of respondents are convinced that for the development of sumo in the Kharkiv region it is necessary to intensify marketing activities of the regional Federation, increase the number of broadcasts of competitions and educational and entertainment programs about sumo on television and create official websites of federations and clubs on the Internet and social networks, while the least effective, according to respondents, is the way of implementing sumo with the help of government leverage, like sumo introduction in educational institutions and financial ensuring a sport from the state budget.

Research on marketing activity in sport [4; 9; 13] show that the effective functioning and strategic directions of development of non-Olympic sports depend on the variability of political and legal factors. Dependence on the power and political stability of the state is defined as the first factor in the further effective operation; competition and competitiveness should

also be taken into account, the services market should be explored, the range of services increased and their quality, effective advertising and strategy of promotion of their services in the market. It can be stated that the Kharkiv Regional Sumo Federation, on the recommendations of interviewed residents of the region, should develop a marketing strategy for the development of sumo, through which to promote services in the market of physical culture and sports services.

In our study, in addition to studying public opinion on the development of sumo in the Kharkiv region, the opportunities and threats of the external environment of the Kharkiv regional sumo federation in the current market conditions (Table 1) were identified. It should be noted that the indicators that scored less than 60 points are threats to the development and implementation of the marketing concept, and the indicators that scored 60 points or more – the possibilities of the marketing environment of the federation.

Table 1
Assessment of opportunities and threats to the activities of the Kharkiv Regional Sumo Federation, according to a survey of specialists in the field of physical culture and sports (n=15)

No.	Evaluation indicators	Sum (Σ)	$\bar{x} \pm m$	%
1.	Expansion of the range	65	4,26±0,23	60,0
2.	Improving the quality and advertising of its services	60	4,00±0,84	80,0
3.	Legislative changes	62	4,13±0,34	70,6
4.	Popularization of the sport (sumo)	70	4,66±0,34	62,6
5.	Political changes in the country	35	2,33±0,05	80,0
6.	Level of inflation in the country	26	1,73±0,28	88,6
7.	Increased mortality	16	1,07±0,06	72,3
8.	Changing preferences of the population by sport	54	3,60±0,30	72,0
9.	Changing the level of income	44	2,93±0,34	79,6

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_{i\max} = 75 \quad \sum_{i=1}^n x_{i\min} = 15$$

From table 1 it is clear that according to experts, the greatest opportunities for further development of the Federation are opened by popularization of sumo among the population and expansion of the range of the Federation itself, quality improvement and advertising of its services, as well as legislative changes. On the other hand, the greatest threat to the development of the Federation is an increase in the mortality rate among the population, inflation and political changes in

the country, a somewhat smaller negative impact on the development of the Federation has a change in income levels and preferences of the population by sport. So, taking into account the risks and using all your available resources of the Federation, you should look for ways of further development and competitiveness in the modern services market.

Important, in our opinion, was the fact that the results of a sociological study are confirmed by expert estimates about the possibilities for the further development of sumo in the Kharkiv region thanks to the effective marketing activities of the Federation.

Conclusions / Discussion

The study characterized the structure of the government of sumo in the world and Ukraine, analyzed the main constituent goals and activities of the Kharkiv Regional Sumo Federation, as a public organization of sports and sports orientation, which complemented the study of N. Dolbisheva on the non-Olympic sport management system. The scientific search of S. Bezkorovaynyi, S. Korobko, V. Yaremenko, I. Milansky, M. Kolos, V. Shandrigos on the application of sumo elements in educational institutions and out-of-school educational institutions was extended. Expanded data from previous studies on the development of non-Olympic sports in the Kharkiv region [1; 7], in particular, found that today in the region, 94 athletes are engaged in sumo, 11 of whom are members of the national team of Ukraine; ordinary citizens showed that 48,7% of respondents consider sumo as an unpopular sport in our country, 76% of respondents are not interested in this kind of sport at all, and only 4,3% are interested, while there is a low level of public awareness about sumo in this region. 80% of the respondents consider it necessary to develop sumo in the Kharkiv region, in their view, should increase the marketing activities of the regional Federation, increase the number of broadcasting competitions and informative and entertainment programs on the sumo on television and create official websites of federations and clubs on the Internet and pages in social networks. Experts estimate that the greatest opportunities for the further development of the federation are the popularization of the sumo among the population and the expansion of the range of the federation itself, improving the quality and advertising of its services, as well as legislative changes. It should be noted that according to ordinary citizens and according to experts, the state should have the least impact on the development of sumo in our country and on the activities of the Federation.

Prospects for further research in this direction are to study the international experience of marketing activities of the governing bodies in non-Olympic sports.

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Information about the Authors

Bairamov Ruslan Khalik ogly: *Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture: 99 Klochkivska Str., Kharkiv, 61058, Ukraine.*

ORCID.ORG/0000-0001-8204-5533

E-mail: bayramov16031990@ukr.net

Anastasia Bondar: *PhD (Physical Education and sport); Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture: Klochkivska str., 99, Kharkiv, 61058, Ukraine.*

ORCID.ORG/0000-0002-2816-4985

E-mail: anastasiabond1@ukr.net